

ON THE CONSISTENCY OF THE VERY FOUNDATIONS OF PHYSICS

July 8, 2024

ABSTRACT: Modern physical theories are beset by the issue of how quantum theory can be consistent with relativity theory. One aspect of such a consistency is related by the incompatibility of free will at the foundations of quantum theory and the stubborn determinism that follows from special relativity theory. The present paper takes into issue such consistency problems and is divided into three parts. Firstly, we present the principles of physical determinism that follow from special relativity theory in the Putnam-Rietjik argument for determinism in the very foundations of physics. Secondly, we present the elements of the principles of contextuality in the Kochen-Conway free will argument..Thirdly, we propose a compatibilist argument the indicates a way out of the foundational inconsistency indicated in the previous sections. As conclusion, argue that both theories are meant to be compatible and that compatibilism is a program for the foundations of physics.

1 Introduction

In a correspondence with Einstein, Max Born raised an important question on the relation of determinism with the seeming liberty of the physical quantum of action. Einstein followed Spinoza in many of his writings keeping faith with the deterministic picture¹ and this was the general trait of the classical theory of physics, which is consistent with the Special Theory of Relativity. Concomitantly, with the benchmark event of the Quantum Paradigm in Physics, the classical deterministic picture of physical theory has been challenged. Einstein himself challenged the classical view² by intuitions stating the violation of the rigorous causality in Quantum Mechanics. Max Born, a long-stand defender of the Quantum Statistical Paradigm and of liberty amid the physical world, criticized Einstein's views³, Hutchson, 1982. by posing a question about the

¹Cf, e.g. Spinoza's Ethics, part I, proposition 29

²Cf. Letter to Heisenberg, June 10, 1927, Albert Einstein Archive, 174.

³See, e.g., The End of Certain World: The life and Science of Max Born. See also The Restless Universe, by Max Born, Dover Publications. Another defender of the chance in Physical Theory was Heisenberg in his books, one of which is worth mentioning: Physics and Philosophy: The Revolution in Modern Science. Born viewpoint was argued further by

consistency requirement in the very foundations of the physical theories. The problem is about the consistency of the liberty of actions in general with the determinations of physical laws⁴. As some remarked along the intellectual path of Einstein, Born posed a consistency question in the form of a dilemma⁵: at one side, there was Born with the indeterministic view or a quantum tychism (chance), of nature and, on the other, there was Einstein with a stubborn determinism about the physical nature and the weakness or akrasia of the human liberty in relation with the natural laws⁶.

Einstein was the first to grasp the intuition meaning a more intense logical and mathematical implication of the Quantum Paradigm, with which Born would have wholeheartedly agreed: the *quantum contextuality* footnoteSee Max Born, *The Natural Philosophy of Cause and Chance*. Ulan Press, 2012, for a defense of liberty amid the world and the quantum, or quantum-paradigmatic notion of physical liberty or *the argument for quantum free will*⁷.

The Einstein-Born Debate indicates a philosophical issue, a very important one, at the very foundations of physical theory. It is about the consistency or compatibility of the indeterminism of free will or liberty with the stubborn strictly causative and determinative character of the physical law⁸. The philosophical inconsistency is both internal and external to Einstein's views on the physical nature.

With the historical preliminary points hitherto indicated, I would like to consider, in this paper, the purpose of discussing the foundational inconsistency in the foundations of the physical theory.

2 A Foundational Consistency Issue and Some Approaches

Now with the previous historical introduction of the Einstein-Born debate, I would like to address two consequences of such a debate, one philosophical and the other mathematical. The philosophical implication has to do with the macrolevel of physics, with the Special Theory of Relativity: *the Putnam-Rietjik Argument*; whereas the second is a rigorous mathematical theorem that follows from the Quantum Paradigm: the quantum liberty theorem or *the free will theorem*.

In the case of the large level of nature using three principles formulated

Popper in his book titled *Quantum Theory and Schism in Physics*

⁴See Born letter to Einstein, Oct 10, 1944, in Born 2005, 150.

⁵See some statements about the issue discussed in the book *Philosophical Problems of Quantum Physics* by Werner Heisenberg, The Oxford Press, 1979.

⁶Cf. On the Quantum Theory of Radiation, Aug 24, 1916, *Collected Papers of Albert Einstein*, 38

⁷Einstein to Max Born, Apr 27, 1924, *Albert Einstein Archives*, 8-176. Also *Sources of Quantum Mechanics*, Dover Books on Physics, 2007.

⁸Cf. Hans Georg Viereck, *Glimpse to the Great*, 1935, in which Einstein declared himself to be a determinist about the laws of nature.

based on the Special Theory of Relativity, Hilary Putnam⁹ put forward a rigorous proof of determinism, an argument that is based on three assumed premises grounded on the time flow view of the specious present, a view that he had called “man on street view” for the concept of reality as the actuality of the physical events in the space-time reference systems. From the three assumptions consistent with the Special Theory of Relativity, Putnam concluded that the reality of future events is predetermined. Other theoretical positions such as Rietjik’s Relativistic Determinism and Penrose’s¹⁰ “Andromeda Paradox” had also deduced and pointed out such a deterministic implication. From the Quantum Paradigm viewpoint, one has to point out the noteworthy *free will theorem*, the Kochen-Conway Argument¹¹. for, so to speak, the liberty of the quantum of action in nature. They had argued from three axioms postulated, namely, FIN, SPIN, and TWIN grounded, respectively, on the quantum measurement theory, the entanglement principle, and the subliminal relativistic communication of any two quantum systems using light signals. This work is a remarkable criticism of the deterministic quantum theories, such as the Einsteinian hidden variable theories.

There are some ways of getting a way out of the foundational inconsistency or foundational dilemma discussed here. Some proposals of reconciling¹² the classical level and the quantum level described by the contemporary Quantum Paradigm would be those like, e.g., Penrose’s New Physics approach¹³, some worked in an ontological framework of reconciling the opposite views for determinism and indeterminism. As examples, we may mention

Khan’s Principles of Physical Monadology for the classical level¹⁴, and I may add another noteworthy work, which was considered as a direct application of natural philosophy, was that of Gale on Geoffrey Chew’s work on hadrons bootstrap model¹⁵.

Therefore, I would like to state that the purpose of research is the examination of the question of consistency of these two remarkable results related to the foundations of physics. The Einstein-Born debate¹⁶ seems to assume a more precise and both logical and mathematical shape. This happens with the

⁹Time and Physical Geometry, The Journal of Philosophy, 64 (8):240-247 (1967).

¹⁰Penrose, Roger (1989). The Emperor’s New Mind: Concerning Computers, Minds, and the Laws of Physics. Oxford University Press. pp. 392–393.

¹¹13 Foundations of Physics 36 (10): 1441. :quant-ph/0604079. Bibcode:2006FoPh.36.1441C. doi:10.1007/s10701-006-9068-6.arXiv.

¹²For a work on the perspectives for the reconciliation of opposite views at the very foundations of physics, let us consider Readhead’s paper titled Relativity and Quantum Mechanics: Conflict of Peaceful existence ? Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences 480(1):14 - 20 · December 2000.

¹³Cf. The Big, The Small and the Human Mind, Oxford University Press, chap. 2 especially. Also The Road to Reality, Vintage Books, 2007.

¹⁴The Principles of Reciprocity and Equivalence of Monads and Their Implications, Nuovo Cimento, Vol. LVII, B, N.2, Oct. 1968.

¹⁵Chew’s Monadology, Georg Gale, Journal of the History of Ideas, Vol. 35, No. 2 (Apr. - Jun 1974) pp.339-48. University of Penn Press.

¹⁶For a remarkable experiment against the Hidden Variable Theory, we shall examine <http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v526/n7575/full/nature15759.html>.

comparison of relativistic determinism with the quantum free will or quantum liberty which lays amidst the contemporary physical theory. I propose to bring the consistency issue referred to herewith into discussions and develop my take on the Einstein-Born dilemma.

3 A Way of Approaching the Issue

To reconcile the Putnam-Rietdijk argument for determinism with the Simon-Kochen theorem in the context of the Dirac electron theory, we need to explore the formal aspects of determinism, non-contextuality, and the implications of quantum mechanics. The Putnam-Rietdijk argument is rooted in the philosophy of time and determinism, asserting that if the future and past are equally real, then the universe is deterministic. This view is often supported by the block universe theory in special relativity, where time is treated as a dimension similar to space, leading to the idea that the future is as fixed as the past. Mathematically, in a deterministic framework, the state of a system at any time t is determined by its state at any prior time t_0 . For a system described by a wavefunction $\psi(t)$, this can be represented by the unitary evolution:

$$\psi(t) = U(t, t_0)\psi(t_0),$$

where $U(t, t_0)$ is the time-evolution operator satisfying the Schrödinger equation. The Simon-Kochen theorem (Kochen-Specker theorem) deals with the issue of hidden variables and non-contextuality in quantum mechanics. It states that it is impossible to assign definite values to all quantum observables simultaneously while maintaining non-contextuality (the value assigned to an observable is independent of other compatible measurements). Mathematically, if $\{A_i\}$ is a set of observables, the theorem shows that no function $v : \{A_i\} \rightarrow R$ can satisfy: 1. ****Non-contextuality****: $v(A_i)$ is independent of the measurement context. 2. ****Functional Relations****: If $f(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) = 0$ for some functional relation, then $f(v(A_1), v(A_2), \dots, v(A_n)) = 0$.

4 Dirac Electron Theory

The Dirac equation for an electron is:

$$(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m)\psi = 0,$$

where ψ is a four-component spinor, γ^μ are the Dirac gamma matrices, and m is the electron mass. To reconcile determinism with the Simon-Kochen theorem in the context of the Dirac electron theory, we need to consider the following:

1. ****Quantum State Evolution****: The deterministic evolution of the quantum state (Putnam-Rietdijk argument) can be expressed by the Dirac equation. The state ψ evolves deterministically according to:

$$\psi(t) = U(t, t_0)\psi(t_0),$$

where $U(t, t_0)$ is derived from the Dirac Hamiltonian H_D :

$$H_D = \gamma^0 m + \gamma^0 \gamma^i p_i.$$

2. ****Measurement Context and Non-Contextuality****: The Simon-Kochen theorem imposes constraints on the assignment of values to observables. In the Dirac theory, observables include the components of the spin and momentum. Due to the theorem, the values of these observables cannot be pre-assigned in a non-contextual manner:

If $\{A_i\}$ are observables, then $v(A_i)$ cannot be non – contextual.

3. ****Compatible Observables and Contextuality****: Consider the observables A, B, C in the Dirac theory where $[A, B] = [B, C] = [A, C] = 0$. The Simon-Kochen theorem states that no single assignment $v(A), v(B), v(C)$ exists such that:

$$f(v(A), v(B), v(C)) = 0,$$

for all functional relations f satisfied by A, B, C .

4. ****Interpretation and Determinism****: The deterministic evolution of the quantum state is not violated by the Simon-Kochen theorem. Instead, the theorem highlights the contextuality of quantum measurements. Therefore, the Dirac equation provides a deterministic evolution of the state, while the contextual nature of measurement outcomes aligns with the Simon-Kochen theorem:

$\psi(t) = U(t, t_0)\psi(t_0)$ is deterministic, while $v(A_i)$ is contextual.

5 Conclusion

In summary, the Putnam-Rietdijk argument for determinism is consistent with the deterministic evolution of the quantum state described by the Dirac equation. The Simon-Kochen theorem addresses the non-contextuality of measurement values, which does not conflict with the deterministic evolution but instead informs us about the contextual nature of quantum measurements. Therefore, the deterministic dynamics of the Dirac electron theory can coexist with the contextual assignment of observable values as required by the Simon-Kochen theorem.

We may conclude as well that the compatibility just sketched in this article can be considered as a program for future physics and it depends on the present state of research in the unification theories of physics. Notwithstanding the difficulties of the unification programs in contemporary physics, we state that compatibilism has a starting point of departure from Dirac's electron theory.